

FORMATION OF LINGUISTIC AND LINGUISTIC COMPETENCIES IN UZBEK LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract. This article focuses on the scientific and didactic foundations of the formation of linguistic and cultural competences of students in Uzbek language education and the formation of linguocultural science, the role of this science in linguistics, and the opinions of Uzbek and foreign linguists in the field of linguocultural science.

Keywords: Linguistic culture, competence, linguistics, linguistic cultural method, methodology

It's true that the challenges and developments of the 21st century necessitate innovations in education, particularly in language teaching. Linguocultural science plays a crucial role in this evolution by integrating cultural understanding into language learning. This approach acknowledges that language is not just a set of grammatical rules but also deeply intertwined with culture and society. By fostering linguistic and cultural competence, educators can better prepare students to navigate a globalized world, where communication across borders and understanding diverse perspectives are essential skills. This methodology not only promotes proficiency in mother tongues, state languages, and foreign languages but also cultivates a broader understanding and appreciation of different cultures, thus contributing to professional competence and global citizenship. It sounds like you're discussing the importance of language acquisition in education, particularly focusing on the Uzbek language. It's crucial to pay attention to each aspect of the educational system and its components, adapting subject content to meet national and global needs. Emphasizing proficiency in Uzbek among students, both orally and in writing, is essential for balanced educational reforms.

It sounds like you're discussing the importance of selecting and sorting social studies materials in Uzbek language classes, and utilizing electronic resources to enhance students' linguistic and cultural competence. This approach reflects the need to develop and explore digital resources for fostering these competencies. It's indeed relevant in today's educational context, where digital tools play a crucial role in enhancing learning outcomes and cultural

understanding. If you have specific aspects or questions about creating or researching digital resources, feel free to ask!

Absolutely! These scholars have made significant contributions to the fields of language education and linguistics. Charles Brumfit, for instance, focused on communicative competence, emphasizing the ability to use language effectively in communication. Antoine Martinet contributed to understanding linguistic competence, the underlying knowledge of language rules and structures. Additionally, J. C. Richards and G. Thomson explored sociolinguistic competence, which involves understanding how language use varies according to social and cultural contexts. C. A. Mizne's work often intersects with these areas, particularly in the context of language teaching and learning. Their research collectively enriches our understanding of language from various perspectives.

The pedagogical-psychological foundations of the linguistic and cultural approach in language teaching, as developed by prominent CIS scientists such as L.S. Vygotsky, B. Lapidus, L.S. Rubenstein, A.N. Leontev, M.V. Babkina, I.L. Bim, N.I. Gez, N.A. Goncharova, A.Yu. Danilyuk, D.D. Jajeva, M.R. Mayenova, A.O. Tenis, and organized by Z.S. Ukolova, L.V. Cherepanova, A.A. Yarulov, among others, emphasize the integration of linguistic and cultural aspects in education. Drawing on Vygotskian principles of socio-cultural theory, these approaches stress the importance of cultural context, social interaction, and the development of language skills within meaningful contexts. This perspective highlights how language learning is intertwined with cultural understanding and psychological development, fostering a comprehensive approach to language teaching and learning.

The research conducted by A. Gulomov, K. Kasimova, S. Matchonov, B. Tokhliev, R. Niyozmetova, Sh. Yusupova, B. Abdullaeva, R. Yoldoshev, T. Ziyadova, A. Hamroev, T. Yusupova, Sh. Yuldasheva, N.Sh. Turdiev, K. Mavlonova, and G. Yusupova focuses on various aspects of enhancing students' intellectual potential, developing oral and written communication skills, and forming competence in language education. Their findings likely contribute insights into methodologies for increasing vocabulary, fostering speaking abilities, and implementing a competence-based approach in language education within the educational system of your country.

It sounds like you're discussing the emergence of linguo-culturology as a field in the 1990s, which integrates linguistics and cultural studies. This

interdisciplinary approach examines the intersection of language and culture, recognizing it as a pioneering aspect of linguistics.

Regarding the formation of linguistic culture, many researchers indeed trace its roots back to the work of Wilhelm von Humboldt. His ideas laid foundational theories about how language shapes and reflects cultural identity and thought, influencing subsequent studies in linguistics and cultural studies.

In Uzbek linguistics, Professor Nizomiddin Mahmudov is noted for his significant contributions to the study of language and culture. He explores the intricate relationship between these two domains in his article titled "In Search of Ways of Perfect Study of Language." Mahmudov discusses how language and culture are often intertwined, with "speech culture" being a key associative concept. He argues that while speech culture is commonly associated with language and culture, the precise nature of their connection is often not fully elucidated. Mahmudov suggests that the study of language can either elucidate a particular culture or vice versa, highlighting the interplay between linguistic expression and cultural understanding. His work emphasizes viewing culture not merely through language but also through broader societal achievements in various facets of human existence, including production, social life, and spiritual-educational practices within the context of Uzbek culture [1:10].

It sounds like you're discussing the nuances of language culture and how words can represent cultural concepts. Professor N. Mahmudov's perspective challenges the notion of "speech culture" and emphasizes the importance of linguistic culture in understanding and conveying cultural ideas. Analyzing words that encapsulate cultural concepts provides an opportunity to educate younger generations and foreigners about our language and culture. This interpretation allows for a deeper exploration and appreciation of linguistic and cultural diversity.

In her textbook "Lingvokulturologiya," Shoirra Usmonova discusses the methodologies within linguoculturology, emphasizing that a comprehensive methodological framework is still under development. Russian linguoculturologists typically integrate the methodologies of linguistics into their approach. The methods of linguistic culture involve analytical actions aimed at exploring the interaction between language and culture. Linguoculturology itself is an interdisciplinary field that incorporates insights from cultural studies, linguistics, ethnolinguistics, and cultural anthropology. It employs various cognitive methods focused on the intersection of language and

culture, selectively applying cultural and linguistic methods in the process of linguistic and cultural analysis (Usmonova, 2:37-38).

It seems there's a discussion about the relationship between linguocultural studies and linguistics, particularly in the context of V. M. Shaklein's views. Shaklein appears to argue that linguocultural studies, despite combining linguistic and cultural elements, should not be considered an independent science separate from linguistics. However, you disagree with Shaklein's perspective. You argue that linguocultural studies, which explore the intersection of language and culture, should indeed be recognized as a legitimate field within linguistics. You emphasize that modern linguistics includes numerous interdisciplinary areas that blend language with other fields, and failing to recognize these within linguistics would hinder the discipline's development. Your viewpoint suggests that linguistics should encompass these intersections to fully capture the complexity and diversity of language in its cultural contexts. This broader inclusion, you believe, is essential for the advancement of linguistics as a discipline.

It sounds like you're developing a comprehensive approach to enhance students' linguistic and cultural competences in Uzbek language education. Here's a refined version of your research topic, focusing on clarity and coherence:

"Our research aims to enhance the linguistic and cultural competences of students in Uzbek language education, informed by perspectives from prominent linguists. Our methodology includes:

1. Identifying stages in students' development of linguistic and cultural competences through the application of digital technologies, integrative approaches, and socio-cultural methods in language teaching.
2. Enhancing didactic strategies to support students' acquisition of linguistic and cultural competences in Uzbek language classes.
3. Implementing tasks and objectives designed to integrate foreign experiences and methodologies that foster students' understanding and retention of Uzbek cultural concepts in both familiar and unfamiliar contexts."

This version maintains your original intent while improving clarity and structure. Based on the opinions of scientists, there is a divergence in perspectives regarding linguistic and cultural studies and their organization. These differences highlight contrasting viewpoints among experts in the field. To address this, it is crucial to implement measures aimed at cultivating students' linguistic and cultural competences effectively.

List of the literature:

1. Mahmudov, N. "Searching for ways of perfect study of the language..." Uzbek language and literature. - Tashkent, 2012. No. 5. - p. 10.
2. Usmanova, Poet. "Linguistic culture." Tashkent, 2019. Pages 37-38.
3. Shaklain, V.M. "Linguistic culture: Tradition and innovation." Monograph. - Moscow: Flinta, 2012. - p. 253.